

FACTORS OF ECONOMIC DIMENSION ON STUNTING IN LAMPUNG PROVINCE, INDONESIA

HUSNA PURNAMA

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University, Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: husnapurnama123@gmail.com

TOTO GUNARTO

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University, Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: toto.gunarto@feb.unila.ac.id

IDA BUDIARTY

Faculty of Economics and Business, Lampung University, Lampung Province, Indonesia.
Email: ida.budiarti@feb.unila.ac.id

Abstract

Purpose: This study analyses the influence of economic dimensions on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province, with the stunting budget as a moderating variable. **Methodology/approach:** The analysis uses the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) models. **Results/findings:** The results of the study indicate that in the economic dimension, income, savings, and own home ownership have a significant adverse effect on the risk of stunting. Moderation analysis shows that the stunting budget moderates the relationship in this dimension, where an increase in the budget strengthens the influence of income, savings, and home ownership on reducing the risk of stunting. The results of the hypothesis support the Human Development Theory, which emphasises the importance of economic investment, and the Socio-Economic Theory, which explains that increasing economic resources breaks the cycle of poverty. **Limitations:** The study only looked at the economic dimension; it did not examine other dimensions, such as the social and health dimensions. **Contribution:** These findings emphasise the importance of multidimensional budget-based interventions as a priority project by the Government in accelerating stunting reduction in Lampung Province.

Keywords: Stunting, Stunting Budget, Economic Dimension, Social, Health, MRA, OLS, Human Development Theory, Socio-Economic Theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Stunting is one of the nutritional problems experienced by toddlers and is currently a global concern. Reducing stunting by 40 per cent in toddlers is the first target of 6 targets set in the worldwide nutrition target 2025 and the leading indicator in the SDGs of Zero Hunger (WHO, 2014).

According to UNICEF data (2016), children with low socioeconomic status have twice the risk of experiencing stunting compared to children from prosperous families. Some social and economic factors, like family income, the number of family members, and the level of education of the parents, can affect the number of stunted children.

Stunted children do not get enough of the proper nutrients, making them more likely to get sick (Pehlke et al., 2016; WHO, 2017; Keino S. et al., 2014). Many factors cause stunting, and these factors are interrelated with each other, such as one of them being

the economy. Family socio-economics is one factor that determines the amount of food available in the family, thus determining the family's nutritional status, including influencing child growth (Gibney et al., 2008). The incidence of stunting is influenced by socio-economic factors, namely those referring to education, occupation, income, social class, race, and gender. Family income affects feeding patterns.

If family income increases, the provision of side dishes will also increase in quality. It is undeniable that family income also affects the food served to the family every day, from the quality to the quantity of food (Nuraeni et al., 2020).

Stunting hampers economic growth and labour market productivity, namely, reducing adult workers' income by 20 per cent, worsening inequality, reducing 10 per cent of total lifetime income, and causing intergenerational poverty (Ministry of Finance processed from the World Bank Investing in the report (Early Years brief, 2016). In this case, community per capita income through family income is related to providing family food, access to food, and adequate food distribution for the family.

The purchasing power for nutritious food in the family is influenced by family income because determining the type of food to be purchased depends on the income level. With a high income, it is possible to meet the food needs of all family members, especially food with excellent quality and nutrition for the family's nutritional intake (Omondi & Kirabira, 2016).

However, on the other hand, low family income levels result in low household food purchasing power (Adriani, 2014). Low purchasing power for food causes the nutritional needs of toddlers to be met (Ranoor, 2010). Children's stress is greatly influenced by socio-economic conditions and the role of parents, especially mothers and fathers. Parents with low socio-economic status tend to be at higher risk of having children who experience stunting.

The unavailability of work for parents can limit their ability to manage food choices and access to health services, directly impacting the quality of children's nutrition. In contrast, parents with adequate income have better access to nutritious food and medical services, which can reduce the risk of stunting.

Economic difficulties in obtaining health services are also a significant factor in the high stunting rate (Aminath Adeela & Dr Kay Seur, 2016). Sari et al. (2020) researched factors influencing stunting in Indonesia.

This study investigated the relationship between economic growth, poverty, and stunting that occurred in Indonesia, which was conducted during the period 2015-2017 in 34 provinces.

This study found that there was an indirect link between the level of poverty and the number of stunted children on long-term economic growth, with stunted children having a more significant impact on slowing down economic growth. There is no evidence that economic growth or poverty causes stunting.

The multifactorial cause is that the socioeconomic dimension significantly influences families at risk of stunting. Children from the poorest households, especially boys, have higher rates of stunting, with socioeconomic inequality increasing over time. Despite national economic progress, these results emphasise the importance of improving the socioeconomic status of poor households to effectively reduce stunting (Coretta M. P. Jonah, 2018).

The importance of income and savings in reducing the risk of stunting is seen in their ability to increase family purchasing power. Ensure kids are fed wholesome meals and have improved sanitary and medical facilities access.

While savings offer financial stability for improved health care, higher wages allow families to meet the dietary demands of their children. For instance, studies by Leroy et al. (2015) demonstrate that by expanding access to improved nutrition and medical care, rising household wealth can lower the prevalence of stunting.

Furthermore, Alderman and Headey (2014) discovered that children's nutritional status and risk of stunting are significantly impacted by household income and the distribution of food expenditures. It has been demonstrated that a high family income considerably lowers a child's risk of stunting.

According to a study of nine central studies involving 21,741 participants from Ethiopia, Nigeria, and Zambia, a higher family income reduces the incidence of stunting by 0.53 times, with the results being somewhat consistent.

According to a 2019 study by Dake et al. (2019), the risk of stunting decreased by 0.20 times. The risk decreased by 0.55 and 0.56 times, respectively, according to other research by Gelu et al. (2017) and Muche et al. (2021). These findings support the significance of family income in boosting food purchasing power and diversifying children's diets to avoid stunting (Wahyuni et al., 2023).

The potential of money and savings to improve family purchasing power for wholesome food and access to quality health and sanitation services demonstrates the significance of these factors in lowering the risk of stunting. While savings offer the financial stability for improved health care, higher income enables families to meet the dietary demands of their children.

For instance, studies by Leroy et al. (2015) demonstrate that by expanding access to improved nutrition and medical care, rising household wealth can lower the prevalence of stunting. Furthermore, Alderman and Headey (2014) discovered that children's nutritional status and risk of stunting are significantly impacted by household income and the distribution of food expenditures.

The number of stunting-risk families with income and savings in 15 districts and cities in Lampung Province is described below.

Source: <https://siga.bkkbn.go.id/> Lampung Province data, 2020-2023.

Figure 3: Average family income and savings in families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province, (2020). –2023

Note: **Family with Saving** **Family with Income**

Based on data on families at risk of stunting who have income and savings, the three regions with the highest income are South Lampung (282,894), East Lampung (282,633), and Central Lampung (208,563). Both South Lampung and East Lampung have very high incomes, reflecting substantial economic potential, with East Lampung having slightly higher savings (253,192).

Despite its lower income, Central Lampung shows a higher savings rate (265,974), which could indicate better savings habits in the region. In contrast, the three areas with the lowest savings are Pesisir Barat (29,471), Way Kanan (101,141), and Mesuji (46,818).

Pesisir Barat has the lowest income and savings, reflecting that this area is quite tricky economic conditions. Way Kanan and Mesuji have slightly higher incomes. However, their savings are still relatively low, indicating that even though there is a higher income, obstacles to saving remain due to limited economic resources.

Most cases of stunting in children occur in families with incomes below the minimum wage. Family income is one of the indicators determining economic status, where high family income can meet family needs and incredibly diverse food needs so that food intake in toddlers can be met; high income also influences families to have savings/savings in the family. This condition will affect the quality of food consumption among family members and be a picture of a good nutritional assessment (Tisna et al., 2021).

Homeownership factors, whether rented or contracted, can affect the risk of stunting in children through several dimensions, especially related to economic stability and access to a healthy environment. Families who own a home tend to have higher housing stability than those who live in rented or contracted homes.

Families with their own homes have more control over the home environment, cleanliness, and facility maintenance, which can affect their well-being. The following is a description of the number of families at risk of stunting from home ownership in 15 districts/cities in Lampung Province:

Source: Lampung Province data, 2020–2023, <https://siga.bkkbn.go.id>. The average number of dwellings owned, rented, or contracted by stunting-risk households in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province is displayed in Figure 4.

Note: **Rented House Families** Families with their own houses

A considerable percentage of households in several regions own and rent or lease their homes, according to data on home ownership status among families at risk of stunting. The three regions with the highest proportion of home-owning families at risk of stunting are South Lampung (94,779), East Lampung (179,766), and Central Lampung (190,007).

Better house ownership rates are found in certain areas, which may indicate the family's financial stability. On the other hand, Central Lampung (101,622), East Lampung (93,138), and South Lampung (91,672) have the highest numbers of households renting or leasing homes; families in these regions are more likely to rent than to own their own homes. In areas like Tulang Bawang (4,261) and Pesisir Barat (12,502), where fewer families rent homes, families are more likely to own their homes despite having low incomes.

This can result from regional laws that encourage property ownership or cultural considerations. In general, areas with higher home ownership rates can indicate more stable economic situations. In contrast, those with higher rental rates typically point to difficulties in obtaining real estate and ensuring families' financial security.

The prevalence of stunting is strongly influenced by the state of a livable home, which is linked to homeownership. This demonstrates how a healthy living environment, including access to necessities like potable water and sanitary restrooms, promotes healthy infant development and avoids stunting. Tamar (2023). The elimination of stunting can be significantly impacted by having a decent home. A good home will encourage a healthy lifestyle and enhance family life, both of which have an impact on children's health and help to prevent stunting.

According to Marsella Arlin Permatasari (2023), a good home also offers a better setting for promoting the distribution of wholesome food and raising parental knowledge and participation, notably among dads, in the fight against stunting. The prevalence of stunting is significantly influenced by whether a residential home is owned or rented.

According to WHO guidelines and the Indonesian Minister of Health Regulation, owned homes typically offer stability and improved access to essential services, including clean water, sanitary conditions, and appropriate waste disposal—all of which are markers of environmental health. On the other hand, children who live in rental homes are more likely to have stunting because they have less access to these amenities.

Stunting cases can be reduced by having access to clean water, adequate sanitation, and appropriate waste management, according to research by Sutarto et al. (2018), Nisa et al. (2021) and Inamah et al. (2021). High stunting rates can be exacerbated by rental housing situations that do not adhere to environmental health regulations. Family income, savings, and property ownership significantly influence stunting risk. Families with high incomes can better receive health care, buy wholesome food, and save money for unexpected expenses. A well-maintained home lowers the risk of illness, promotes child development, and produces a healthy atmosphere. In order to improve family welfare and lower the incidence of stunting, these three elements work together.

Concerning the Economic aspects of income and savings growth in 15 Lampung Province districts and cities, stunting is more common in families with incomes below the local minimum wage. This indicates that the likelihood of stunting is seven times higher when family wealth is taken into account (Nasikhah & Margawati, 2012).

According to another study, toddlers who live with more than five family members are about twice as likely to suffer from stunting as toddlers who live with two to four family members (Fikadu et al., 2014). Food availability is impacted by the number of family members residing in a single home; Arifin asserts that the lower the household's food security, the higher the food expense. This has to do with getting the meal (Arifin, 2004).

An overview of income and savings in 15 districts and cities in Lampung Province is provided below:

Figure 17: In 15 regencies and cities in Lampung Province, the average percentage of stunting-risk families with income and savings in 2021–2023

Note: Having Saving Having Income only

According to data on families at risk of stunting who have savings and income, South Lampung (15.40%), East Lampung (15.38%), and Central Lampung (11.35%) have the most significant percentage of these families. Despite having income, the quality of life or income distribution in these locations is insufficient to reduce the risk of stunting, as seen by the high numbers. In contrast, Pesisir Barat (1.93%), Metro City (2.24%), and Way Kanan (2.58%) have the lowest percentages in this group, indicating poorer economic circumstances among stunting-risk families.

Central Lampung (15.67%), South Lampung (13.18%), and East Lampung (14.92%) lead the savings category, suggesting that while high-income families are more likely to have money, the risk of stunting is still significant. On the other hand, Pesisir Barat (1.74%), Metro City (2.22%), and Mesuji (2.76%) have the lowest percentages, indicating more severe economic limitations.

To sum up, the areas with the highest numbers need interventions that encourage the best use of income and savings to satisfy the nutritional needs of families and raise income. However, to improve the purchasing power and financial stability of families at risk of stunting, the regions with the lowest percentages need a more all-encompassing economic strategy.

1.1 Formulation of the Problem

The formulation formed in the Economic dimension with six important variables so that the formulation of the problem is formed:

- a. How is the influence of families with income, families without income, families with savings, families without savings, home ownership, and rental/contracted home ownership on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province?
- b. How is the influence of families with income, families without income, families with savings, families without savings, home ownership, rental/contracted home ownership, and stunting budget on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province?
- c. How does the stunting budget change the relationship between economic factors affecting families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province?

1.2 The Objectives

The objectives are formed in the economic dimension with six important variables so that the formulation of the problem is formed:

- a. Testing and empirically analysing the influence of families with income, families without income, families with savings, families without savings, own home ownership, and ownership of rented/contracted houses on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province.
- b. Testing and analysing the effects on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies and cities in Lampung Province of families with income, families without income, families with savings, families without savings, families who own their own homes, families who rent or lease homes, and families with and without stunting budgets.
- c. Testing and empirically analysing the influence of stunting budgets in intervening by moderating the relationship between economic dimensions, which include families with income, families without income, families with savings, families without savings, own home ownership, and ownership of rented/contracted houses, on families at risk of stunting in 15 regencies/cities in Lampung Province.

1.3 Contribution of Research

The following are the contributions derived from the study's findings:

- a. This study makes significant methodological and theoretical advances that the economic factors influencing stunting and the impact of budgeting as a moderating variable will be examined from several perspectives. The budget interventions can reduce the impact of these determinants on the likelihood of stunting more effectively than previous approaches when using Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA).
- b. This study makes empirical contributions by thoroughly examining 15 districts and cities in Lampung Province; this study generates insights pertinent to regional decision-making by utilising contextualized and detailed local data.

- c. This study makes a policy contribution by highlighting the significance of economic budgetary initiatives that enhance maternal health, parenting education, and nutritional status, where economic variables can reduce the prevalence of stunting.
- d. It is hoped that the findings of this study will serve as a point of reference or study material for further research, which will strengthen and rectify any shortcomings found in this study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1 Theory of Human Development

Expanding human choices is known as human development (UNDP, 1990). UNDP first presented this idea as an enhancement of earlier GDP-based human resource analysis. Because of economic differences, average income does not always represent the well-being of society.

Five key concepts form the foundation of human development: (1) prioritising people, (2) providing them with more options in life rather than merely more money, (3) enhancing their intelligence and capacity, (4) advancing the four key pillars of empowerment, sustainability, equity, and productivity, and (5) applying these concepts to the formulation of development objectives.

Human development prioritises four key areas in order to accomplish its objectives:

- 1) Productivity: boosting human capital by investment in people.
- 2) Equity—ensuring everyone has equal access to social and financial resources.
- 3) Sustainability: Future demands must be taken into account when developing.
- 4) Empowerment: Individuals should be involved in choices impacting their lives.

Human development is measured by the three main components of the Human Development Index (HDI) (UNDP, 1990).

- 1) Life Expectancy Index: indicates the community's average age and level of health.
- 2) The Decent Living Index is a gauge of economic well-being based on GDP per capita.
- 3) The Education Index measures the level of knowledge among people aged 15 and older by considering literacy rates and the average length of education.

2.2 Theory of Socioeconomics

"Social" refers to society and the part of society that puts the public interest first, according to KBBI. Social conduct is a reflection of how people cooperate to achieve their needs. Economics, on the other hand, deals with how people try to develop ways to meet their demands for well-being.

Gerungan (2009) lists the following as some parental social aspects that affect a child's development:

- 1) Family Integrity
- 2) Attitudes and behaviours of parents.
- 3) Status of the child.

2.3 Socioeconomic Classification and Level

According to Coleman and Cressey in Sumardi (2004), two primary criteria exist for classifying socioeconomic status. Wealthy people with authority and the ability to adequately meet their basic requirements, such as conglomerates, are considered to be of upper socioeconomic status. On the other hand, people with lower socioeconomic status are less wealthy and socially prominent and frequently struggle to meet their necessities.

2.4 Stunting

A loss of adequate growth brought on by chronic starvation is known as stunting. The TB/U Z-score value is calculated using WHO 2007 anthropometry to determine stunting status (UNICEF, 2013). Stunting is a public health issue since it raises the risk of illness and both mental and physical growth retardation.

A height-for-age index below -2 SD from the WHO growth standard is considered stunting, a form of malnutrition (WHO, 2012). The primary causes of stunting are infectious diseases, an imbalanced diet, and the cycle of poverty; these factors exacerbate children's nutritional status and are interrelated (WHO, 2020).

Stunting has a highly negative effect on kids. According to WHO (2020), its effects can be classified as either short-term (such as higher mortality and morbidity and impaired cognitive, motor, and linguistic development) or long-term (such as short stature, obesity risk, and lower economic productivity).

2.4.1 Indicators of Stunting

A key metric for differentiating between stunting and expected growth in children is their height for age (H/A). Anthropometrically, height is a measure of skeletal growth.

2.4.2 Elements Influencing Stunting and Government Regulations Regarding Stunting

Children who are stunted have difficulties growing and developing. They are either taller or shorter than typical. A height for age z-score above two standard deviations below the WHO (World Health Organization)-recommended median child growth indicates this (Organization, 2018).

Stunting can result from a variety of factors, including the educational status of the parents (particularly the mother), age at pregnancy, socioeconomic status, nutritional status of the mother, infectious diseases, and other health conditions during pregnancy, as well as the

prenatal conditions of the child (particularly the mother), including birth weight, premature birth, breastfeeding exclusively, nutritional intake status, infectious diseases in infancy, and a host of other factors depicted in the figure below (Santosa et al., 2022).

Figure 10: Multifactorial Factors Affecting the Incidence of Stunting in Mothers and Children Stunting prevention's primary challenges include insufficient program efficacy and collaboration between

The multifaceted issue of stunting is linked to parenting styles, maternal nutrition, and access to medical services like postnatal care and antenatal care (ANC). Stunting risk is increased by a combination of economic, social, and health variables (TNP2K, 2017).

Access to public services like health and education is influenced by a family's economic standing, which in turn influences the nutritional quality of children. Families in good financial standing have easier access to food and medical care. Since family income is the primary indicator of economic status, stunting is more prevalent in households with incomes below the minimum wage. Families with high incomes are better able to save money and meet a variety of food needs, which raises the standard of food consumption. This reflects excellent nutritional status (Tisna et al., 2021).

Several factors, such as parenting styles, family income, and the mother's education, cause stunting. Stunting can be avoided with interventions like more nutrient-dense food programs. Basic food needs can be better met by families with a healthy income (Lidia Hastuti, 2024).

Environmental variables also impact family health, particularly housing quality, waste management, and sanitation. A healthy environment protects Children from illness, which lowers the risk of illness and medical costs (Bhutta, 2008; Mary, 2018). Stunting risk can be decreased by decent, well-maintained housing, typically privately held (Mutia Citrawati Lestari, 2023).

The type of food that can be bought is determined by family income, which also affects the availability of household necessities. Family eating choices are also influenced by income (Adriani & Wirjatmadi, 2014).

Higher education also improves one's chances of landing a better-paying job, yet time-consuming work can make parents less attentive to their kids (Adriani, 2012). A habitable home with good sanitation fosters a healthy atmosphere and aids in the development of young people. These three elements are crucial for enhancing family well-being and lowering the incidence of stunting. The preceding description generates the following theories regarding the economic dimension:

- H1 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to be significantly impacted negatively by families with income (MP).
- H2 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to benefit significantly from families without income (TDK_MP).
- H3 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to be significantly impacted negatively by families with savings (MT).
- H4 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to benefit significantly from families without savings (TDK_MT).
- H5 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to be negatively impacted by home-owning families (RMH_S).
- H6 = Families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) are thought to benefit significantly from the presence of rented or contracted housing owners (RMH_SK).
- H7 = Families at risk of stunting are thought to be significantly and negatively impacted by the stunting budget (KK_RS).
- H8 = The link between families with income (MP) and families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) is thought to be negatively and significantly moderated by the stunting budget (AS). The impact of income on lowering the risk of stunting increases with the size of the budget.
- H9 = The association between low-income households (TDK_MP) and stunting-risk families (KK_RS) is thought to be favourably and considerably moderated by the stunting budget (AS). (The effect of not having savings on raising the likelihood of stunting is reduced by increasing the stunting budget).
- H10 = The association between families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) and families with savings (MT) is thought to be adversely and significantly moderated by the stunting

budget (AS). The impact of savings on lowering the risk of stunting increases with the size of the budget.

H11 = The link between families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) and families without savings (TDK_MT) is thought to be positively and considerably moderated by the stunting budget (AS). (The effect of not having savings on raising the likelihood of stunting is reduced by increasing the stunting budget).

H12 = The association between home-owning families (RMH_S) and stunting-risk families (KK_RS) is thought to be adversely and significantly moderated by the stunting budget (AS). The impact of home ownership on lowering the risk of stunting increases with the size of the stunting budget.

H13 = The link between families at risk of stunting (KK_RS) and those who own rented or contracted dwellings (RMH_SK) is thought to be positively and considerably moderated by the stunting budget (AS). The framework for considering the social dimension is as follows:

2.5 Conceptual Framework

A comprehensive strategy incorporating poverty reduction tactics, raising household income, and guaranteeing access to wholesome food is needed to lower stunting in Lampung Province. The relationship between economic determinants and stunting levels must be evaluated to maximise treatments. The estimated variables in the economic dimension are as follows:

Figure 11: Framework for Economic Dimensions

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This quantitative descriptive study uses provided, processed, and interpreted quantitative data to address problems. The secondary data was acquired indirectly from various sources, including official websites, data-gathering books, and periodicals.

Secondary data is released by the Directorate General of Fiscal Balance (DJPK), the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), and the Family Data Information System (SIGA) BKKBN. These sources are located in Lampung Province and are at the city or district level. In addition to several other pertinent publications

Panel data, or a mix of time series data and cross-sectional geographical observations, is used in this study. While the cross-sectional data includes 15 districts/cities in Lampung Province, the time series data used spans the years 2020–2024. As a result, this study's observations comprise 75 data points.

Families at Risk of Stunting are the dependent variable in this study, while the independent variables contribute to, affect, or affect the research findings (outcomes) (Creswell, 2014).

The components that make up the independent variables in this study are the economic, social, and health dimensions. Additionally, the budget is included as a moderating variable in this study.

Five years of data collection from 15 districts/cities in Lampung Province (pooled) served as the basis for the OLS (Ordinary Least Square) panel data regression model to choose the panel data for this study. While cross-sections are employed because data is collected from different regions, time series are required because the study spans five years.

The typical effect, fixed effect, and random effect approaches are the three methods used to estimate panel data regression models. Three different types of approaches are used in panel data estimation: Random Effect (REM), Fixed Effect (FEM), and Common Effect (PLS). T

Three tests are used to identify the optimal approach, including analysing the p-value. Juanda & Junaidi (2012) employ the Chow Test to identify the superior model between CEM and FEM. In contrast, the Hausman test looks at the p-value to identify which of the FEM and REM models is the best (Juanda & Junaidi, 2012).

To determine which of the CEM and REM models is best, we apply the Breusch-Pagan test. By looking at the chi-squared value and the Lagrange multiplier test value, we do the Breusch-Pagan test (Widarjono, 2017).

The Normality Test is used in the Classical Assumption Test to determine whether or not the error term is regularly distributed. If the normalcy assumption is unmet, the t-statistic test invalidates the testing process.

**Table: Definition Operational, Symbols, Data Sources and Study Previous
 Variables Dimensions Economy**

No	Variables	Definition Operational	Symbol	Unit	Researcher Previous
1	Family Own Income	Family own income is for 6 (Six) Months Finally, there is at least 1 (one) member family that has source income for fulfil need principal per month. This means family the own access to income that is me they for sufficient need base like food, clothes, places stay and need essential other in a way monthly. Condition This reflects existence ability economy in a family to endure alive, even though the level of income or contribution from member of the family can varies in accordance with the type of work or source of income owned. Source: Https://Siga.Bkkbn.Go.Id/	MP	Person /Fam	(Agustin, 2021), (Tisna, et al 2021). (Lidia Hastuti , 2024). (Adriani And Wirjatmadi , 2014). (Adriani , 2012).
2	Family No Own Income	Family No own income is for 6 (Six) Months Lastly, no there is at least 1 (one) member family that has source income for fulfil need principal per month. That means deep period said, family No own capable members produce sufficient income for sufficient need base like food, clothes, places stay, and need essential others. Conditions This show that family is at in situation tough economy and very depends on help external, such as help social or support from party others, for fulfil need life daily. Source: Https://Siga.Bkkbn.Go.Id/	TDK_MP	Person /Fam	(Agustin, 2021), (Tisna et al, 2021). (Lidia Hastuti, 2024). (Adriani and Wirjatmadi, 2014). (Adriani, 2012).
3	Family Have Savings	Family own savings or savings in form Money cash, jewelry, animals livestock, results garden, or asset others that can used at any time For fulfil need main in 3 (three) months to front. This is show that family own backup economy that can reliable as source Power for overcome need urge or face situation emergency. Savings This reflect ability family for plan finance and guard sustainability fulfillment need base in term short, though No always covers need term long. Source : Https://Siga.Bkkbn.Go.Id/	MT	Person /Fam	(Omondi Kirabira, 2016). (Adriani, 2015). (Ranoor, 2010). (A, Chowdhury S, 2006). (De Pee S, ,2010), (Ardani DWSR, Wulandari M, Suharmanto S, 2020).
4	Family No Have Savings	Family No own savings or savings in the form of Money, cash, jewellery, animals, livestock, results garden, or assets	TDK_MT	Person /Fam	(Omondi & Kirabira, 2016). (Adriani, 2015).

No	Variables	Definition Operational	Symbol	Unit	Researcher Previous
		others that can used at any time for fulfilling need main in 3 (three) months to front. This is show that family is at in situation very economic vulnerable, without backup source power that can reliable for face need urge or situation emergency. In condition this, family fully depends on income daily, help social, or support from other party to sufficient need basic, so that more prone to risk economy and uncertainty. Source : https://Siga.Bkkbn.Go.Id/			(Ranoor, 2010). (A, Chowdhury S, 2006). (De Pee S, ,2010), (Ardani DWSR, Wulandari M, Suharmanto S, 2020).
5	House Alone	House Alone is ownership House in context family. This used for measure whether family live in a house owned Alone or occupy place live. occupied house is owned by family in a way law or based on confession custom. This status can proven with document official like certificate land or document right owned by other. Source : https://siga.bkkbn.go.id/	RMH_S	Person /Fam	(A. Hoque Chowdhury et al., 2013; Osmani & Sen, 2011) . (Sutarto et al, 2018) (Nisa et al, 2021), (Inamah et al, 2021),
6	House Rent / Contract	House rent / contract refer to on place status where does the family live or individual living in a house that is not his, but occupied with pay cost rent in term time certain. Occupied house based on agreement rent with payment periodically, such as monthly or annual. Owner House still hold right ownership, while tenant own right use temporary in accordance agreement. Source : https://siga.bkkbn.go.id/	RMH_SK	Person /Fam	(A. Hoque Chowdhury et al., 2013; Osmani & Sen, 2011) . (Sutarto et al, 2018) (Nisa et al, 2021), (Inamah et al, 2021),

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Estimation Results and Discussion of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

The selection of panel data regression estimation techniques is known to have 3 types of estimation approaches, namely *fixed effect*, *random effect*, and *common effect*.

To determine the best technique to be used for panel data regression, tests are carried out, namely the chow test, the hausman test, and the LM test.

a. Chow Test

Table 5: Chow/Fixed Effect Test Results

No Budget Model			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	df	Prob
Cross-section F	2.68737	(14.54)	0.0047
Cross-section Chi-square	39.6525	14	0.0003
Models on a Budget			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	df	Prob
Cross-section F	45.063120	(14.53)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	191.812195	14	0.0000
Model with <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i> Budget			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	d,f,	Prob
Cross-section F	20,8273	(14.47)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	148,0966	14	0.0000

Source: Eviews 9, Data processed 202 4.

Note : Critical Value at 0.05

Based on table 5. The Chow Test shown above, the following are the results of testing the Model without Budget, Model with Budget and Model with Budget *Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)* with Economic Dimensions, Social Dimensions and Health Dimensions, resulting in a probability level <0.05, thus causing Ho to be rejected, so *the fixed effect model* is significant and can be used in panel data regression.

b. Hausman test

Table 6: Results of the Husman/Random Effect Test

No Budget Model			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F Random	9,8701	6	0.0130
Models on a Budget			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F Random	35,860321	7	0.0000
Cross-section F Random	62.837251	7	0.0000
Model with <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i> Budget			
Economic Dimension Model	Statistics	df	Prob.
Cross-section F Random	75,7488	13	0.0000
Cross-section F Random	48,8628	13	0.0000

Source: Eviews 9, Data processed 2024.

Note : Critical Value at 0.05

Based on table 6. The Hausman test shown above is the test result of the Model without Budget, Model with Budget and Model with Budget *Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)* with Economic Dimension, Social Dimension and Health Dimension produces a probability level <0.05, thus causing Ho to be rejected, then *the fixed effect model* is significant and can be used in panel data regression.

c. Lagrange Multiplier (LM) Test

Based on the results of the Chow Test and the Hausman Test, the most appropriate model is shown, namely *Fixed Effect*. Therefore, the *Lagrange Multiplier Test* is not used in this study and *the Lagrange Multiplier Test* can be ignored (Widarjono, 2013).

4.2 Testing Classical Assumptions

a. Multicollinearity Test

Table 8: Results of Multicollinearity Testing without Budget

Economic Dimensions without Budget			
NO	Variables	VIF	Information
1	Have Income (MP)	2,2497	In the Level of Tolerance
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	1,3412	In the Level of Tolerance
3	Have Savings (MT)	2.3375	In the Level of Tolerance
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	1,4992	In the Level of Tolerance
5	Own House (RMH_S)	1,1035	In the Level of Tolerance
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	1,0128	In the Level of Tolerance

Table 9: Results of Multicollinearity Testing with Budget

Economic Dimensions without Budget			
NO	Variables	VIF	Information
1	Have Income (MP)	2,2497	In the Level of Tolerance
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	1,3412	In the Level of Tolerance
3	Have Savings (MT)	2,3375	In the Level of Tolerance
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	1,4992	In the Level of Tolerance
5	Own House (RMH_S)	1,1035	In the Level of Tolerance
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	1,0128	In the Level of Tolerance
7	Stunting Budget (BUDGET)	2,1891	In the Level of Tolerance

Table 10: Results of Multicollinearity Testing of the Model with *Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Budget*

Economic Dimension with Budget <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i>			
NO	Variables	VIF	Information
1	Have Income (MP)	8,8105	In the Level of Tolerance
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	7,4515	In the Level of Tolerance
3	Have Savings (MT)	3,1162	In the Level of Tolerance
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	3,8900	In the Level of Tolerance
5	Own House (RMH_S)	3,3579	In the Level of Tolerance
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	3,3333	In the Level of Tolerance
7	Stunting Budget (M_BUDGET_Z)	1,9191	In the Level of Tolerance

Source: Data processed 2024,

Based on table 8, table 9, table 10 above, the results of the Multicollinearity level test show that *the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)* values of all independent variables have values <10, this explains that the three models have values at the tolerance level i.

4.3 Autocorrelation Testing

Table 11: Results of Autocorrelation Problem Detection

Economic Dimensions Without Budget			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
6	15.45	14.07	Free with <i>Coef Covariance Method</i>
Economic Dimension with Budget			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
7	5,111	14,607	Autocorrelation Free
Economic Dimension with Budget <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i>			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
13	25.17	22,362	Free with <i>Coef Covariance Method</i>

Source: *Eviews processed data, 2024*

Based on table 11 above, the steps in overcoming Autocorrelation in the final model are carried out using the *white method* to eliminate the autocorrelation problem by changing *the Coef Covariance Method* to *White-Cross section* in *the option panel* so that it changes the regression equation to be free from autocorrelation problems. The conclusion of the final model in the regression is that it is free from autocorrelation problems and the hypothesis has rejected H_0 .

4.4 Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 12: Results of Heteroscedasticity Problem Detection

Economic Dimensions Without Budget			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
6	11,445	12,592	Free from Heteroscedasticity
Economic Dimension with Budget			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
7	7.7625	14,607	Free from Heteroscedasticity
Economic Dimension with Budget <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i>			
Independent Variable	Chi-Square Calculation	Chi Square Table	Conclusion
13	8,355	22,362	Free from Heteroscedasticity

Source: *Eviews processed data, 2024*

Steps to overcome Heteroscedasticity in the final model are carried out using the *Cross-section Weights method* to eliminate the Heteroscedasticity problem by changing *the GLS Weights* to *Cross-section Weights* in the panel option so that the regression equation is free from the Heteroscedasticity problem (Widarjono, 2013). The conclusion of the final model in the regression is that it is free from the heteroscedasticity problem and the hypothesis has rejected H_0 .

4.5.1 Results of Ordinary Least Square (OLS) and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Estimation on Panel Data

a. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Estimation Results without Budget

Table 20: Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Results on the Fixed Effect Model of Economic Dimensions without Budget

Dependent Variable: KK_RS				
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)				
Sample: 2020 2024				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 75				
Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix				
White cross-section standard errors & covariance (df corrected)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MP	-0.074058	0.018464	-4,010880	0.0002**
TDK_MP	0.016284	0.003144	5,179093	0.0000**
MT	-0.317870	0.010522	-30,21100	0.0000**
TDK_MT	0.013830	0.004472	3.092744	0.0031**
RMH_S	-0.005966	0.001270	-4.697511	0.0000**
RMH_SK	0.000195	0.001368	0.142862	0.8869
C	14,86762	0.214737	69.23640	0.0000
R-squared	0.985034	Mean dependent variable		31.60857
Adjusted R-squared	0.979492	S,D, dependent var		16.62532
S,E, of regression	0.256164	Sum squared residual		3.543480
F-statistic	177,7145	Durbin-Watson stat		1.212068
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews, Data processed 2024

Description: Critical Value on:

* : Based on 99% confidence level ($\alpha=1\%$)

** : Based on 95% confidence level ($\alpha=5\%$)

*** : Based on 90% confidence level ($\alpha=10\%$)

() : t-Statistic

The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Mathematical Model, shows the results of the regression calculation which is then transformed into a mathematical form, then the mathematical model by entering the equation values from the regression as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 KK_RS_{it} = & 14,86762 - 0,074058MP_{it} - 0,317870MT_{it} - 0,005966RMH_S_{it} \\
 & (-4.010880) (-30.21100) (-4.697511) \\
 & + 0,000195RMH_SK_{it} + 0,016284TDK_MP_{it} + 0,013830TDK_MT_{it} \\
 & (0.142862) (5.179093) (3.092744)
 \end{aligned}$$

b. Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Estimation Results with Budget

Table 23: Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Results on the Fixed Effect Model of the Economic Dimension with Budget

Dependent Variable: KK_RS				
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)				
Sample: 2020 2024				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 75				
Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix				
White cross-section standard errors & covariance (df corrected)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
MP	-0.018643	0.006796	-2.743323	0.0083**
TDK_MP	0.003865	0.007803	0.495260	0.6225
MT	-0.019795	0.005492	-3.604331	0.0007**
TDK_MT	0.318341	0.041251	7.717128	0.0000**
RMH_S	-0.011848	0.003109	-3.810870	0.0004**
RMH_SK	-0.008983	0.012764	-0.703753	0.4847
STUNTING_BUDGET	-0.042531	0.019638	-2.165679	0.0349**
C	6.920023	0.613056	11.28775	0.0000
R-squared	0.997808	Mean dependent variable		14,56874
Adjusted R-squared	0.996940	S, D, dependent var		9.731748
S, E, of regression	0.091159	Sum squared residual		0.440424
F-statistic	1149,071	Durbin-Watson stat		1.322592
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews, Data processed 2024

Description: Critical Value on:

- *: Based on 99% confidence level ($\alpha=1\%$)
- ** : Based on a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=5\%$)
- ***: Based on 90% confidence level ($\alpha=10\%$)
- () : t-Statistic

The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Mathematical Model shows the results of the regression calculation, which is then transformed into a mathematical form, then the mathematical model by entering the equation values from the regression as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 KK_RS_{it} = & 6,920023 - 0,018643MP_{it} - 0,019795MT_{it} - 0,011848RMH_S_{it} \\
 & (-2.743323) (-3.604331) (-3.810870) \\
 & -0,008983RMH_SK_{it} + 0,003865TDK_MP_{it} + 0,318341TDK_MT_{it} - 0,042531ANGGARAN_{it} \\
 & (-0.703753) (0.495260) (7.717128) (-2.165679)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.3 Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Estimation Results with Budget Moderation

Table 26: Results of Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) in the Fixed Effect Model of Economic Dimensions

Dependent Variable: KK_RS				
Method: Panel EGLS (Cross-section weights)				
Sample: 2020 2024				
Periods included: 5				
Cross-sections included: 15				
Total panel (balanced) observations: 75				
Linear estimation after one-step weighting matrix				
White cross-section standard errors covariance (d.f, corrected)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob,
MP	-0.007937	0.000884	-8,976768	0.0000**
TDK_MP	0.000516	0.000214	2.408931	0.0200**
MT	-0.000207	7.64E-05	-2,710454	0.0094**
TDK_MT	0.017725	0.001951	9.083769	0.0000**
RMH_S	-0.003699	0.003258	-1.135426	0.2620
RMH_SK	0.017859	0.004253	4,198986	0.0001**
STUNTING_BUDGET	-0.003101	0.000255	-12,17642	0.0000**
BUDGET_MP	-0.146229	0.039179	-3,732361	0.0005**
BUDGET_TDK_MP	0.166980	0.030490	5.476493	0.0000**
BUDGET_MT	-0.004123	0.001555	-2.652058	0.0109**
BUDGET_TDK_MT	0.113535	0.003699	30,69600	0.0000**
BUDGET_RMH_S	0.035143	0.033966	1.034665	0.3061
BUDGET_RMH_SK	1.024193	0.040970	24.99836	0.0000**
C	1.474678	0.148184	9.951632	0.0000
R-squared	0.999998	Mean dependent variable		18,13763
Adjusted R-squared	0.999998	S, D, dependent var		10.22284
S, E, of regression	0.000767	Sum squared residual		2.76E-05
F-statistic	1106340,	Durbin-Watson stat		1,487052
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Eviews, Data processed 2024

Description: Critical Value on:

- *: Based on 99% confidence level ($\alpha=1\%$)
- ** : Based on a 95% confidence level ($\alpha=5\%$)
- ***: Based on 90% confidence level ($\alpha=10\%$)
- () : t-Statistic

The Mathematical Model of *Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)* shows the results of regression calculations, which are then transformed into mathematical form, then the mathematical model by entering the equation values from the regression as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 KK_{RS_{it}} = & 1,474678 - 0,007937MP_{it} - 0,000207MT_{it} - 0,003699RMH_{S_{it}} \\
 & (-8.976768) (-2.71045) (-1.135426) \\
 & + 0,017859RMH_{SK_{it}} + 0,000516TDK_{MP_{it}} + 0,017725TDK_{MT_{it}} \\
 & (4.198986) (2.408931) (9.083769) \\
 & -0,003101A_{STUNTING_{it}} + 1,024193A_{RMH_{SK_{it}}} + 0,035143A_{RMH_{S_{it}}} \\
 & (-12.17642) (24.99836) (1.034665) \\
 & -0,00412A_{MT_{it}} - 0,14622A_{MP_{it}} + 0,16698A_{TDK_{MP_{it}}} + 0,16698A_{TDK_{MT_{it}}} \\
 & (-2.652058) (-3.732361) (5.476493) (30.69600)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

a. t-Test Results (Partial)

Table 13: Results of t-test without budget

Economic Dimension				
No	Independent Variable	t-count	t-table	Conclusion
1	Have Income (MP)	4,010880	1,6680	H ₀ Rejected
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	5,179093	1,6680	H ₀ Rejected
3	Have Savings (MT)	30,21100	1,6680	H ₀ Rejected
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	3.092744	1,6680	H ₀ Accepted
5	Own House (RMH_S)	4.697511	1,6680	H ₀ Rejected
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	0.142862	1,6680	H _a Rejected

Table 14: Results of t-Test with Budget

Economic Dimension				
No	Independent Variable	t-count	t-table	Conclusion
1	Have Income (MP)	2.743323	1.66792	H ₀ Rejected
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	0.495260	1.66792	H _a Accepted
3	Have Savings (MT)	3.604331	1.66792	H ₀ Rejected
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	7,717128	1.66792	H ₀ Rejected
5	Own House (RMH_S)	3,810870	1.66792	H ₀ Rejected
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	0.703753	1.66792	H _a Accepted
7	Stunting Budget (BUDGET)	2,165679	1.66792	H ₀ Rejected

Table 15: Results of the t-test with Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) Budget

Economic Dimension				
No	Independent Variable	t-count	t-table	Conclusion
1	Have Income (MP)	8.976768	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
2	No Income (TDK_MP)	2.408931	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
3	Have Savings (MT)	2,710454	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
4	Have No Savings (TDK_MT)	9.083769	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
5	Own House (RMH_S)	1.135426	1,6700	H _a Accepted
6	Rental/Contract House (RMH_SK)	4,198986	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected

7	Stunting Budget (M_BUDGET_Z)	12,17642	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
8	Budget*Has Income (MP)	3.732361	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
9	Budget*No Revenue (TDK_MP)	5.476493	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
10	Budget*Have Savings (MT)	2.652058	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
11	Budget*No Savings (TDK_MT)	30,69600	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected
12	Budget*Own Home (RMH_S)	1.034665	1,6700	H _a Accepted
13	Budget*Rental/Contract Housing (RMH_SK)	24.99836	1,6700	H ₀ Rejected

Source: Data processed 2024.

b. F-Statistic Test Results

Table 16: Results of the F test at a 95 per cent confidence level

Economic Dimensions Without Budget				
Independent Variable	F-count	F-Table	Prob	Conclusion
6	177,7145	2,348	0.0000	Ho was rejected
Economic Dimension with Budget				
Independent Variable	F-count	F-Table	Prob	Conclusion
7	1149,071	2,240	0.0000	Ho was rejected
Economic Dimension with Budget Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)				
Independent Variable	F-count	F-Table	Prob	Conclusion
13	110,6340	1,9100	0.0000	Ho was rejected

Source: Data processed 2024.

c. Results and Analysis of Individual Effects

Table 17: Individual Effect Results in 15 Districts/Cities Without Budget

Economic Dimensions Without Budget				
No	CROSSID	Effect	C	Individual Effect
1	Lampung Selatan	1,4188	14,8676	16,2864
2	Lampung Tengah	1.5217	14,8676	16,3893
3	Lampung Utara	0.5782	14,8676	15,4458
4	Lampung Barat	-0.4497	14,8676	14,4179
5	Tulang Bawang	-0.9620	14,8676	13,9056
6	Tanggamus	0.5852	14,8676	15,4528
7	Lampung Timur	1,3773	14,8676	16,2449
8	Way Kanan	0.2203	14,8676	15,0879
9	Pesawaran	0.2886	14,8676	15,1562
10	Pringsewu	0.0893	14,8676	14,9569
11	Mesuji	-1.0286	14,8676	13,8390
12	Tulang Bawang Barat	-1.5088	14,8676	13,3589
13	Pesisir Barat	-1.6825	14,8676	13,1852
14	Kota Bandar Lampung	0.9758	14,8676	15,8434
15	Kota Metro	-1.4235	14,8676	13,4441

Table 18: Individual Effect Results in 15 Districts/Cities with Budgets

Economic Dimension with Budget				
No	CROSSFIT	Effect	C	Individual Effect
1	Lampung Selatan	0.641083	6,9200	7,5611
2	Lampung Tengah	0.969026	6,9200	7,8890
3	Lampung Utara	0.43441	6,9200	7,3544
4	Lampung Barat	0.342364	6,9200	7,2624
5	Tulang Bawang	-0.099792	6,9200	6,8202
6	Tanggamus	0.328287	6,9200	7,2483
7	Lampung Timur	0.782593	6,9200	7,7026
8	Way Kanan	-0.157419	6,9200	6,7626
9	Pesawaran	0.295717	6,9200	7,2157
10	Pringsewu	-0.065271	6,9200	6,8547
11	Mesuji	-0.65266	6,9200	6,2673
12	Tulang Bawang Barat	-0.656978	6,9200	6,2630
13	Pesisir Barat	-0.765708	6,9200	6,1543
14	Kota Bandar Lampung	-0.005897	6,9200	6,9141
15	Kota Metro	-1.389756	6,9200	5,5302

Table 19: Individual Effect Results in 15 Districts/Cities with MRA Budgets

Economic Dimension with Budget <i>Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)</i>				
No	CROSSFIT	Effect	C	Individual Effect
1	Lampung Selatan	1.418812	14,86762	16,2864
2	Lampung Tengah	1.521715	14,86762	16,3893
3	Lampung Utara	0.578188	14,86762	15,4458
4	Lampung Barat	-0.449698	14,86762	14,4179
5	Tulang Bawang	-0.962007	14,86762	13,9056
6	Tanggamus	0.585173	14,86762	15,4528
7	Lampung Timur	1,377308	14,86762	16,2449
8	Way Kanan	0.220279	14,86762	15,0879
9	Pesawaran	0.288565	14,86762	15,1562
10	Pringsewu	0.089268	14,86762	14,9569
11	Mesuji	-1.028603	14,86762	13,8390
12	Tulang Bawang Barat	-1.508762	14,86762	13,3589
13	Pesisir Barat	-1.682468	14,86762	13,1852
14	Kota Bandar Lampung	0.975773	14,86762	15,8434
15	Kota Metro	-1.423542	14,86762	13,4441

- a. The results indicate that the presence of family members with income (MP) has a negative and significant effect on the risk of stunting in the family (KK_RS). In the OLS model without control, an increase of 1 family member with income reduces the risk of stunting by 0.07%, while by including the budget variable, the effect becomes 0.018%. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) shows that changing the budget strengthens the effect of MP, lowering the risk of stunting by 0.14%.
- b. The study's results show that no income (TDK_MP) generally has a positive and significant effect on the risk of stunting in the family (KK_RS) in the OLS model. The risk of stunting rises by 0.016% for every additional family member without income. However, the effect is insignificant in the model with the budget variable. Moderated

Regression Analysis (MRA), which has a significant coefficient of 0.166980, shows that the budget has been unable to lessen this lousy effect.

- c. The analysis results show that the presence of family members who have savings (MT) consistently has a negative and significant effect on the risk of stunting in the family (KK_RS). In the OLS model without control, an increase of 1 family member with savings reduces the risk of stunting by 0.31%, while by including budget variables, the effect becomes 0.019%. Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) shows that changing the budget strengthens the effect of MT, lowering the risk of stunting by 0.41%. This finding shows that family savings, especially with the support of budget interventions, play a significant role in effectively reducing the risk of stunting.
- d. The analysis results show that the absence of savings (TDK_MT) consistently has a positive and significant effect on the risk of stunting in the family (KK_RS). In the OLS model without budget variables, an increase of 1 family member without savings increases the risk of stunting by 0.013%. In contrast, the model with budget variables increases the effect to 0.031%. In Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA), changing the budget has not helped lessen the harmful effects of not having savings; the risk of stunting has increased by 0.11%.
- e. The analysis results show that home ownership (RMH_S) generally negatively and significantly affects the risk of stunting in families (KK_RS) in the OLS model. An increase of 1 family with their home reduces the risk of stunting by 0.05%, and in the model with budget variables, the effect increases slightly to 0.011%. In the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) analysis, however, budget intervention did not significantly affect the relationship between home ownership and stunting risk. This suggests that home ownership has a more direct effect that is not affected by budget intervention.
- f. The stunting budget that intervenes in the economic dimension has a negative and significant effect on the risk of stunting in families (KK_RS). In the OLS model, every 1million rupiah increase in the budget reduces the risk of stunting by 0.042%. Meanwhile, in the Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) analysis, the stunting budget still has a negative effect with a risk reduction of 0.0031%.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

5.1 Conclusion

Here are some practical and targeted policy recommendations for 15 districts and cities in Lampung Province based on the analysis of economic issues related to stunting:

- a. Improving Maternal and Child Health Service Budget Allocation in Remote Locations: In distant or difficult-to-reach parts of Lampung, mother and child health services require a unique budget from the local government, including expanding the BPJS Health Program for Poor Families' counselling and access

- b. Nutrition and Health Education Initiative for Families in Communities at Risk for Stunting: Putting in place nutrition and health education initiatives for families in regions like coastal and interior regions where stunting is common.
- c. Improving cities' and districts' access to clean water and sanitary infrastructure. The local authority must prioritise the construction and upkeep of sanitary facilities and clean water access, particularly in areas or cities with high stunting rates.
- d. Campaign to Strengthen Ideal Marriage Age Policy in Certain Areas: This initiative encourages community-based campaigns on the ideal marriage age between 20 and 35 years old and involves community and religious leaders in counselling.

Limitation and Further Research

The study only looked at the economic dimension; it has not yet examined the social and health dimensions. Further research is needed to explore such dimensions, especially concerning budgeting.

Studies on the Effects of Health Budget Interventions on Vulnerable Groups' Stunting The effects of health budget measures on vulnerable populations, such as families with adolescent pregnant moms or mothers from low-income backgrounds, can be the subject of future studies. This will enable a deeper comprehension of how health budgets might be more successful in lowering stunting in specific high-risk groups.

Charting the Performance of Budget Stunting Initiatives Considering accessibility and geographic location, more research can examine the efficacy of stunting budget initiatives based on geographic location, such as disparities between urban and rural areas, given the variations in the availability of health services in different regions. This endeavour will determine whether the amount of money allotted to health impacts stunting risk differently in areas with diverse access to medical care.

A qualitative assessment of how budget programs affect family behaviour in meeting children's nutritional needs; the impact of the stunting budget program on family behaviour in meeting children's nutritional needs can be further investigated through in-depth qualitative research, such as interviews with families who receive benefits. This method allows us to pinpoint the social and cultural obstacles that hinder health budget initiatives' ability to lower stunting effectively.

References

- 1) Agus *Widarjono*, P. (2017). *Ekonometrika Pengantar dan Aplikasinya Disertai. Panduan Eviews*. Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN.
- 2) Agustin, D. Rahmawati (2021). Relationship of Family Income with Stunting Incidence. *Indonesian Journal of Midwifery*, Vol. 4 No. 1. <http://dx.doi.org/10.35473/ijm.v4i1.715>.
- 3) Agustina, R., Weken, M. E., & Anggraeny, D. (2023), Implementation of Health BPJS Usage in Stunting Toddler Management at Stunting Locus: Implementasi Penggunaan BPJS Kesehatan dalam Penanganan Balita Stunting di Locus Stunting. *Amerta Nutrition*, 7(2SP), 7–12.

- 4) Alderman, H., & Headey, D. D. (2014). How important is my household income in determining child malnutrition? *World Development*, 64, 37–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2014.06.010>.
- 5) Alderman, H., Hoogeveen, H., & Rossi, M. (2006). Reducing child malnutrition in Tanzania: Combined effects of income growth and program interventions. *Economics and Human Biology*, 4(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ehb.2005.07.001>
- 6) Aminath Adeela, Dr Kay Seur, (2016), Impact of Maternal Socio-Economic Determinants On Early Childhood Stunting in Maldives: An Analysis of Maldives Demographic Health Survey 2009. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research* Volume 5, Issue 06, June 2016 Issn 2277-8616.
- 7) Andrani, M, Wirjatmadi. (2014). *Pengantar Gizi Masyarakat*. Jakarta: PT. Fajar Interpratama Mandiri.
- 8) Andriani, A. (2012). *Asuhan gizi nutrition care process*. Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu.
- 9) Arifin, B. (2004). *Penyediaan dan Aksesibilitas Ketahanan Pangan (Supply and Accessibility of Food Security)*. Widyakarya Pangan Dan Gizi, 8, 17–19.
- 10) BAPENNAS. (2020). *RPJMN 2020-2024*. In *Rencana Pembangunan Jangka Menengah Nasional 2015-2019*.
- 11) Bhutta, Z. A. (2008). Micronutrient needs of malnourished children. In *Current Opinion in Clinical Nutrition and Metabolic Care*. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MCO.0b013e3282fbf5a0>
- 12) Bhutta, Z. A., Das, J. K., Rizvi, A., & Huicho, L. (2013). *Evidence-based interventions for improvement of maternal and child nutrition: What can be done and at what cost?* *The Lancet*, 382(9890), 452-477. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(13\)60996-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(13)60996-4)
- 13) Bloem MW, Pee SD, Hop LT, dkk. (2013). Key strategies to further reduce stunting in Southeast Asia: Lessons from the ASEAN countries workshop. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*: 34:2.
- 14) Bloem, M. W., de Pee, S., Le Hop, T., Khan, N. C., Lailou, A., Minarto, MoenchPfanner, R., Soekarjo, D., Soekirman, Solon, J. A., Theary, C., & Wasantwisut, E. (2013). Key strategies to further reduce stunting in Southeast Asia: Lessons from the ASEAN Countries Workshop. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin*, 34(2_suppl1), S8– S16. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15648265130342S103>.
- 15) Hoque, et al. "Socio-demographic Factors Associated with Home Delivery Assisted by Untrained Traditional Birth Attendant in Rural Bangladesh." *American Journal of Public Health Research* 1.8 (2013): 226-230
- 16) Coretta M. P. Jonah, Winnie C. Sambu and Julian D. May, (2018) A comparative analysis of socioeconomic inequities in stunting: a case of three middle-income African countries. *Jonah et al. Archives of Public Health* (2018) 76:77 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13690-018-0320-2>.
- 17) Cryer, J. D., (1986), *Time Series Analysis*, PWS-KENT Publishing Company, Boston.
- 18) Dake, S.K., Solomon, F.B., Bobe, T.M. *et al*. Predictors of stunting among children 6–59 months of age in Sodo Zuria District, South Ethiopia: a community-based cross-sectional study. *BMC Nutr* 5, 23 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40795-019-0287-6>
- 19) Fikadu, T., Assegid, S., & Dube, L. (2014). Factors associated with stunting among children of age 24to 59 months in Meskan district, Gurage Zone, South Ethiopia: a case-control study. *Bmc Public Health*, 14(1), 800.
- 20) Fitriani, Barangkau, Masrah Hasan, Ruslang, Eka Hardianti, Khaeria, Resti Oktavia, & Selpiana. (2022). *Cegah Stunting Itu Penting*. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat (JurDikMas)*

- 21) Gelu A, Edris M, Derso T, Abebe Z (2018). Undernutrition and associated factors among children aged 6-59 months living in slum areas of Gondar city, northwest Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study. *Pediatric Health Med Ther*.9: 81–88. doi: 10.2147/phmt. s172317
- 22) Gibney, M, Barrie M, John M dan Lenore Arab (2008). *Gizi Kesehatan Masyarakat*. Jakarta: EGC, 2008.
- 23) Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia. Implementation of Prosperous Family Development. Indonesia. (1994). Available online: <https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Home/Details/57208/pp-no-21-tahun-1994> (accessed on 10 October 2022)
- 24) Inamah, Rahwan Ahmad, Wahyuni Semmeng, Hairudin Rasako. 2020. Hubungan Sanitasi Lingkungan dengan Stunting pada Anak Balita di Daerah Pesisir Pantai Puskesmas Tumalehu Tahun 2020. *Jurnal kesehatan terpadu* Vol 12 No.2. ISSN 1978776 Didownload dari Journal homepage: <https://www.jurnalpoltekkesmaluku.com/index.php/JKT>
- 25) Illahi, Rizki K. (2015). *Hubungan Pendapatan Keluarga, Berat Lahir, Dan Panjang Lahir Dengan Kejadian Stunting Balita 24-59 Bulan Di Bangkalan*. *Jurnal Manajemen Kesehatan Yayasan RS*
- 26) Keino S, Plasqui G dan Borne VD. (2014). *Determinants of stunting and over-weight among young children and adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa*. *Food and Nutrition Bulletin* 35 (2): 167 – 178.
- 27) Kemenkes RI. (2018). *Buletin Jendela Data dan Informasi Kesehatan: Situasi Balita Pendek di Indonesia*, Pusat Data dan Informasi Kementerian Kesehatan RI. Jakarta.
- 28) Kemenkes, R. I. "Peraturan Menteri Kesehatan Republik Indonesia Nomor 2 Tahun (2020) Tentang Standar Antropometri Anak." Jakarta: Menteri kesehatan republik Indonesia.
- 29) Kemenkeu, D. J. A. (2023). *Kebijakan Anggaran Stunting*.
- 30) Kemenkeu, D. J. K. N. (2022). *Pendanaan Penurunan Stunting*. <https://www.djkn.kemenkeu.go.id/kpknl-ternate/baca-artikel/15355/Pendanaan-Program-PenurunanStunting.html#:~:text=Pada tahun 2022%2C pemerintah telah, mendukung Program Percepatan Pencegahan Stunting>.
- 31) Kemenkopmk. (2021). *Menko PMK: Tangani Kemiskinan Ekstrem Dapat Selesaikan Stunting Juga*. Kementerian Koordinator Bidang Pembangunan Manusia dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia. <https://www.kemenkopmk.go.id/menko-pmk-tangani-kemiskinan-ekstrem-dapat-selesaikan-stunting-juga>
- 32) Kementerian Kesehatan RI. (2012). *Advertorial Kesehatan Anak: Umur Sama, Kok Tinggi Beda*. Nova, edisi Juni Minggu kedua 2012, (2015). *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2015*, (2016). *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2016*, (2017). *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2017*, (2018). *Profil Kesehatan Indonesia 2018*.
- 33) Kementerian Kesehatan RI. (2018-2019). *Laporan Riset Kesehatan Dasar 2018*. Kemenkes: Jakarta.
- 34) Kementerian PPN/ Bappenas. (2018). *Pedoman Pelaksanaan Intervensi Penurunan Stunting Terintegrasi di Kabupaten/Kota. Rencana Aksi Nasional Dalam Rangka Penurunan Stunting: Rembuk Stunting*, (November), 1–51. Retrieved from <https://www.bappenas.go.id>
- 35) Leroy, J. L., Ruel, M. T., & Verhofstadt, E. (2015). Household income, expenditures, and child stunting: A cross-country analysis. *Maternal & Child Nutrition*, 11(Suppl 4), 108-124. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mcn.12168>
- 36) Lidia Hastuti, (2024). Relationships Between Family Role with Stunting Incidents in Rural, *international Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT)* ISSN: 2509-0119. © 2024 Scholar AI LLC. Vol. 45 No. 2 July 2024, pp. 58-63.

- 37) Marsella Arlin Permatasari, (2023) Analisis Partisipasi Masyarakat Dalam Mencapai Zero Stunting Di Kelurahan Bulak Banteng Kecamatan Kenjeran Kota Surabaya. Publika. Volume 11 Nomor 4, Tahun 2023, 2637-2650.
- 38) Muche A, Gezie LD, Baraki AG, Amsalu ET. (2021). Predictors of stunting among children age 6–59 months in Ethiopia using Bayesian multilevel analysis. *Sci Rep* 11. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-82755-7.
- 39) Mutia Citrawati Lestari, (2023), Analysis of The Relationship Between Self-Help Housing Assistance Programs and The Reduction of Stunting in Indonesia. *Journal of World Science*
<https://jws.rivierapublishing.id/index.php/jwsVolume2No.8August2023>
DOI: 10.58344/jws.v2i8.3781188P-ISSN: 2828-8726E-ISSN: 2828-9307.
- 40) Nasikhah, R., & Margawati, A. (2012). Faktor risiko kejadian stunting pada balita usia 24–36 bulan di Kecamatan Semarang Timur. Diponegoro University.
- 41) Nasikhah, R., & Margawati, A (2012). Risk Factors for Stunting Incidence in Toddlers Age 24-36 months in Semarang District. Diponegoro University.
- 42) Nisa, Septi Khotimatun, Elisabeth Deta Lustiyati, Ayu Fitriani. (2021). Sanitasi Penyediaan Air Bersih dengan Kejadian Stunting pada Balita. *Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengembangan Kesehatan Masyarakat Indonesia*. Universitas Respati Yogyakarta, Indonesia
- 43) Noor, M.S.; Andrestian, M.D.; Dina, R.A.; Ferdina, A.R.; Dewi, Z.; Hariati, N.W.; Rachman, P.H.; Setiawan, M.; Yuan, W.T.; Khomsan, (2022) A. Analysis of Socioeconomic, Utilization of Maternal Health Services, and Toddler's Characteristics as Stunting Risk Factors. *Nutrients* 2022, 14, 4373. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu14204373>
- 44) Nuraeni, Rina., Suharno (2020), Gambaran Faktor-Faktor yang Berhubungan dengan Kejadian Stunting Balita Usia 24-59 Bulan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia*. 2020; 5(10).
- 45) Omondi DO dan Kirabira P. (2016). *Socio-Demographic Factors Influencing Nutritional Status of Children (6-59 Months) in Obunga Slums, Kisumu City, Kenya*. *Public Health Research* 6 (2):69-75.
- 46) Pehlke EL, Letona P, Hurley K dan Gittel-sohn J. *Guatemalan school food environment: impact on schoolchildren's risk of undernutrition and overweight/obesity*. *Health Promotion International* 2016. 31: 542–550.
- 47) **Pemprov Sulut, P. P. S. U.** (2020). *Penetapan Hasil Kinerja Kabupaten Lokus Dalam Penanganan Konvergensi Stunting Terintegrasi di Provinsi Sulawesi Utara Tahun 2020*.
- 48) Ranoor, R.N.F. (2010). *Hubungan Faktor Sosio-Ekonomi, Tingkat Konsumsi, Status Infeksi, dan Status Imunitas dengan Status Gizi Balita*. Surabaya. Universitas Airlangga.
- 49) Sari, D., Hasanah, I., & Santosa, P. (2020). *Hubungan Pendapatan Keluarga dan Stunting pada Anak di Kecamatan X*. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan Masyarakat*, 8(1), 45-52.
<https://ejournal.unimman.ac.id/index.php/jusika/article/download/275/288/653>
- 50) Sutarto, Diana Mayasari¹, Reni Indriyani. (2018). Stunting, Faktor Resiko dan Pencegahannya. *Jurnal Kedokteran Fakultas Kedokteran, Universitas Lampung*
- 51) Tamar, Erynola Moniharapon, Sophia G. Sipahelut, Meitycorfrida Mailoa, (2023) Faktor–Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Stunting Pada Balita Di Desa Karay dan Desa Angar Kabupaten Seram Bagian Timur. *Jurnal Agrosilvopasture-Tech* Vol. 2 No. 2 (2023) 297-302.
- 52) Tisna Yanti¹, DiahAdni Fauziah (2021), he Effect of Family Income on Stunting Incident inPreschool Children at Bogor City During COVID-19 Pandemic. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, April-June 2021, Vol. 12, No. 2.

- 53) TNP2K, (2017), Buku 100 Kabupaten/Kota Prioritas Untuk Intervensi Anak Kerdil (Stunting), Buku Hak Cipta Dilindungi Undang-undang © 2017 Tim Nasional Percepatan Penanggulangan Kemiskinan, Seketeriat wakil presiden republic Indonesia.
- 54) UNICEF. (2013). Ringkasan kajian gizi. Jakarta: Pusat Promos Kesehatan Kementerian Kesehatan RI.
- 55) Wahyuni SD, Murti B, Adriani RB (2023). Meta-Analysis: Effect of Household Size, Maternal Education, and Family Income on Stunting. J Epidemiol Public Health. 08(03):323-334. <https://doi.org/10.26911/-jepublichealth.2023.08.03.04>.
- 56) Wahyuni, W (2020), The Relation of Stunting with Immunization Status and the History of Low Birth Weight in the Work Area of Public Health Center at Gilingan. Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research, volume 535 Proceedings of the 1st Paris Van Java International Seminar on Health, Economics, Social Science and Humanities (PVJ-ISHESSH 2020)
- 57) Wapres, S. (2019). Strategi Nasional Percepatan Pencegahan Anak Kerdil (Stunting) Periode 2018-2024. In Sekretaris Wakil Presiden (Vol. 01). Sekretaris Percepatan Pencegahan
- 58) WHO. (2016). WHA Global Nutrition Targets 2025: Stunting Policy Brief.WHO: Genewa.
- 59) Worldbank. (2015). *Beban Ganda Malnutrisi Bagi Indonesia*. Diakses dari <http://www.worldbank.org/in/news/feature/2015/04/23/the-double-burden-of-malnutrition-in-Indonesia>